

Atlantis Healing Method has actually been rebuilt and brought to light once again some years ago however the roots of this healing technique come from ancient history and civilization referred to as Atlanteans. Intelligence Atlanteans were using at that period of time was extremely sophisticated and most of it we even do not understand today.

Healing concepts were numerous and based upon Portals of Light and using smart energy as source which is nowadays known as Universal Energy, Scalar Energy etc. It is multidimensional and being transported linking to celestial measurement (source).

Atlantis Energy Healing Method aroused a great deal of interest of energy recovery experts, quantum physics, metaphysics and individuals interested in this type of stuff.

Author of Atlantis Healing reconstruction when explained-- ' Whatever is already there-- we just have to understand how to use it best method.'

It is really intriguing experience throughout the healing session as it enables you to travel through different layers and measurements, some individuals also experience taking a trip through time. Most of the customers experience also pure light which surrounds them as soon the practitioner opens the session linking and activating a special quartz crystal which is programmed to connect to websites of Light. After the session individual primarily experiences gorgeous vibration within the entire body and inner balance which improves significantly currently after the [atlantis healing](#) very first session.

Primarily individuals ask how the session looks like and what is anticipated from individual who goes under this healing session to do or how to collaborate. The response is-- absolutely nothing. A client puts down where ever he can discover a comfortable dark place without being disrupted for an hour. After unwinding the entire body the session starts and can be performed in person as likewise remote (distance between a customer and specialist does not matter nor effect the recovery). A client ought to be aware of objective he has actually for the healing which indicates-- what ought to be a subject of this energy recovery. Professional starts to catalyze his intelligent energy linking customer to crystal and crystal to portals of Light.

Atlantis Healing Energy results may vary from individual to specific however mainly one might see improvements currently instantly after the session. Self-healing processes which have actually been activated during the session might last for a month or more to complete which suggests a individual is improving and much better every day, releasing old past energies which do not serve him anymore and changing them with new vital forces.

We will most likely understand a lot more about this approach in the near future because a lot of investigations are taking place.